

Systematic Review: Examination of Theses Conducted to Determine the Effect of Simulation-Based Education on Nursing Students in Turkey

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this systematic review is to examine postgraduate thesis studies in Turkey that evaluate the effects of simulation-based education on nursing students. A total of five master's and doctoral theses published between 2012 and 2022 were analyzed, obtained from the National Thesis Center of the Council of Higher Education using the keywords "nursing," "patient," and "simulation." The studies were comparatively evaluated in terms of study design, sample size, measurement tools, implementation features, and main findings. Four of the included theses were randomized controlled trials, and one was a quasi-experimental study. Simulation-based education was found to improve students' knowledge levels. Especially, the use of virtual patient simulation and standardized patients had positive effects on self-confidence, clinical decision-making, and communication skills. However, while an increase in knowledge was observed in some studies, statistically significant improvements were not always achieved in practice-based skills such as developing care plans or making nursing diagnoses. Furthermore, simulation alone was found insufficient for long-term learning retention. Theses conducted in Turkey demonstrate that simulation-based education is an applicable and effective method in nursing education. However, its effectiveness depends on structured scenarios, instructor competence, active student engagement, and repeated practice. Future studies are recommended to include long-term follow-ups and support findings with qualitative data.

INTRODUCTION

Simulation, which has various definitions, is described as an instructional method in which a realistic model of an event, activity, or real-life situation is developed, imitated, or constructed under conditions that closely resemble reality. It is also utilized for the development of professional roles and the evaluation of student competencies (1). Simulation creates a realistic representation of a patient's condition to enable students to safely practice skills acquired through education without posing risks to real patients (2). According to another definition by Larew and colleagues, simulation is described as "an artificial representation of a phenomenon or activity that allows participants to experience a realistic situation without the risks of the real world" (3).

In recent years, simulation methods have been increasingly emphasized across various professional fields (4-6). These methods have been applied in program-specific field

laboratories, professional skill laboratories, demonstrations, and clinical case presentations (7,8).

Virtual Reality (VR) is a computer-generated artificial environment investigated through sensory stimuli and represents a socially constructivist approach to learning. It is a powerful educational method that involves students in active participation, problem-solving, and interactive instruction (9,10). It also provides easy access to information during practice and enhances memory retention in the learning process (11). During the design phase of simulation, the implementation standards prepared by the International Nursing Association for Clinical Simulation and Learning (INACSL) should be considered (12,13).

This study aims to examine postgraduate theses conducted in Turkey that evaluate the impact of simulation-based education on nursing students.

METHODS

In this study, registered master's and doctoral theses archived by the Council of Higher Education Thesis Center were reviewed using the keywords "nursing," "patient," and "simulation." As a result, five studies conducted between 2012 and 2022 were identified. Since the research is a systematic review, ethical committee and institutional permissions were not required. The study received no financial support and has no conflict of interest. The characteristics of the theses including degree level, year, type, sample size, measurement tools, intervention properties, and results were summarized.

RESULTS

This retrospective study was conducted between January 1 and 17, 2024, and included five theses that met the inclusion criteria. Among these, one was a master's thesis and four were doctoral theses.

One of the studies was quasi-experimental, and the remaining four were randomized controlled trials. The findings from the master's thesis are presented in Table 1. The findings from the doctoral theses are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Characteristics of the graduate research evaluated.

Employment Name and Year of Publication	Type	Number of Samples	Measurement Tools Used	Application Features	Results Obtained
Şivgin, 2022 (14)	Randomized Controlled Trial	94 students	"Descriptive features form", "Peristomal Skin Lesions Information Test", "Peristomal Skin Lesions Assessment Tool" and "Peristomal skin lesions photographs"	"Pre-test", "theoretical training", "standard patient simulation application to the intervention group", "post-test-1" and "post-test-2" were applied to the researchers 4 weeks after the training. The students in the intervention group of the study were simulated with a standard patient after theoretical training. After the simulation application, post-test-1 was applied to the intervention group. The control group was given post-test-1 after the training.	In the posttest-2 applied 4 weeks after the training; However, there was no statistically significant difference between the groups in terms of information retention ($p>0.05$). There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of the scores of the students correctly identifying the peristomal skin lesion site and type.

Table 2. Characteristics of the doctoral research being evaluated.

Employment Name and Year of Publication	Type	Number of Samples	Measurement Tools Used	Application Features	Results Obtained
Durmaz, 2012 (15)	Randomized Controlled Trial	84 students	The Clinical Decision Making Scale in Nursing was used by adapting it to Turkish. In addition, "pre- and post-operative patient care management cognitive level assessment test"; "Applied deep breathing and	Students received training in computer-aided simulation (n:41) and skills laboratory (n:41). Students were randomly assigned to groups. "Pre- and post-operative patient care management cognitive level assessment test"; "Applied deep breathing and coughing exercise training" and "Admission of the patient from surgery to the clinic" skill checklists and "Clinical Decision Making Scale in Nursing" were applied.	In our country, pre- and post-operative care has been taught by simulation and an example has been set in the education of complex situations in nursing. It should be the responsibility of managers and trainers to use the opportunities provided by technology in solving the low number of trainers, the inadequacy of the

			coughing exercise training" and "Admission of the patient from surgery to the clinic" skill checklists and "Clinical Decision Making Scale in Nursing" were applied.	There is no difference in the post-training knowledge of the students, "applied deep breathing and coughing exercise training" skills, clinical decision-making scale total and sub-dimension score averages. In the third stage of the research; The opinions of the students who received training in the simulation about the educational approach, their learning processes, their perceptions and suggestions about their individual development were evaluated with qualitative research	learning environment and teaching complex subjects.
Onarıcı, 2019 (16)	Randomized Controlled Trial	61 students	"Burnt Patient Care Cognitive Level Assessment Test", "Student Opinions Form for the Effectiveness of the Simulation Method", "Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning Scale", "Simulation Design Scale", "Educational Practices Questionnaire", "Burnt Patient Care Plan Evaluation Form" and "Focus Group Interview Questions"	In the study, pre-test, second test and post-test, knowledge tests, first and second burn patient care plan applications were carried out with all students, and the burn patient scenario application was carried out only with the intervention group. As the last stage of the data collection process, a group of students selected from the intervention and control groups were applied in the burn clinic and a focus group interview was held for the application.	As a result of the research, it was determined that the post-test information scores in the intervention group increased statistically significantly compared to the control group. As a result of the evaluation between the groups of the intervention and control groups, it was determined that there was no significant difference between them in terms of care plan scores ($p>0.05$), and although it was not significant, the second burn patient care plan scores of the intervention group were higher than the control group. It was determined that the increase in the second burn patient care plan nursing interventions score of the students in the intervention group was significant, and the decrease in the total score of the second burn patient care plan in the control group was significant.
Şahin, 2020 (17)	Randomized Controlled Trial	126 students	"Personal Information Form", "Self-Confidence and Anxiety in Clinical Decision Making in Nursing", "Scale for Evaluation of	Students were divided into "virtual patient simulation group", "virtual patient and high reality simulator based simulation group" and "high reality simulator based simulation group" with stratified randomization.	It has been determined that virtual patient simulation is superior to other methods in terms of self-confidence and anxiety, simulation-based learning and performance scores in clinical decision-making in

			Simulation-Based Learning" and "Feedback Form"		nursing. In addition, it has been determined that the use of virtual patient simulation and high-reality simulator-based simulation together provides higher performance than the use of high-reality simulator-based simulation alone.
Akkurt Yalçintürk, 2022 (18)	Randomized Controlled Trial	71 students	"Structured Student Information Form", "Dementia Knowledge Exam", "Case Study Form for Individuals Diagnosed with Dementia", "Standardized Mini Mental Test", "Communication Skills Assessment Form", "Nursing Diagnosis Detection Skill Form" and "Modified-Simulation Effectiveness Tool"	A total of 71 students, 36 in the experimental group and 35 in the control group, completed the study. While the experimental group was trained with standardized patient simulation method, the standard curriculum was followed in the control group.	It has been concluded that standardized patient simulation training is effective in providing nursing students with the ability to provide care for individuals diagnosed with dementia.

DISCUSSION

This systematic review examined master's and doctoral theses evaluating the effects of simulation-based education on nursing students in Turkey. Overall findings indicate that simulation-based education can positively impact both knowledge and clinical practice skills, although statistically insignificant outcomes were also observed in certain cases.

Şıvgın's (2022) study assessed knowledge and diagnostic skills regarding peristomal skin lesions through simulation education. No statistically significant difference was found between the intervention and control groups in terms of knowledge retention after four weeks, suggesting that while simulation may be effective in the short term, it may not alone ensure long-term learning (14). Similarly, literature suggests that simulation is an effective learning tool, yet repeated practice and reinforcement are necessary to enhance knowledge retention (2,11).

Durmaz's (2012) study compared the impact of computer-assisted simulation and skills lab training. No significant differences were found in knowledge, skills, and clinical decision-making (15). Despite the technology level used, these results indicate the importance of how teaching strategies are

implemented (5). However, qualitative evaluations in the third phase of the study revealed students' positive perceptions of the learning process, individual development, and teaching methods (1).

In Onarıcı's (2019) study, simulation practices for burn patient care showed a significant increase in knowledge scores among the intervention group (16). Although no statistically significant differences were found in care plan scores, the significant increase in nursing intervention scores within the intervention group highlighted simulation's supportive role in clinical decision-making and procedural skills (4).

Şahin's (2020) study is notable for comparing different simulation methods. Virtual patient simulation was found to be superior in terms of self-confidence and performance. (17) Moreover, the combination of virtual patient simulation with high-fidelity simulator-based simulation yielded better performance than high-fidelity simulation alone (9).

In Akkurt Yalçintürk's (2022) study, standardized patient simulation was found to be effective in training nursing students to care for individuals with dementia (18). This finding

indicates that simulation can also be used to develop more abstract skills such as communication and decision-making (7).

Overall, the findings support the use of simulation as an effective instructional method in nursing education. However, the level of outcomes achieved varies depending on the type of simulation used, scope of the intervention, evaluation methods, and individual characteristics of students. While knowledge improvement was often observed, some studies did not find significant differences in skills such as care planning or diagnosis. This suggests that simulation should be implemented through long-term and progressive sessions (12).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, postgraduate theses in Turkey demonstrate that simulation-based education is both applicable and effective in nursing education. For simulation to be more impactful, the following considerations are essential:

- Well-structured scenarios
- Ensuring educator competency
- Preference for student-active applications
- Support through long-term and repeated simulation sessions

It is recommended to enhance the effects of simulation education on theoretical knowledge and clinical skills through multidisciplinary approaches. Future studies should include long-term follow-up of learning outcomes and place greater emphasis on qualitative evaluations of students' learning processes.

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